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How cognition and metacognition interact in explaining creative confidence

Lidia Wojtycka, Aleksandra Zielińska, and Maciej Karwowski

University of Wrocław

Authors' Note and Acknowledgements

Lidia Wojtycka, Aleksandra Zielińska, and Maciej Karwowski, Institute of Psychology, University of Wrocław, Wrocław, Poland.

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Please address correspondence concerning this article to Maciej Karwowski (Institute of Psychology, University of Wrocław, Dawida 1, St, 50-527 Wrocław, maciej.karwowski@uwr.edu.pl).

Abstract

In two preregistered experiments ($N = 301$ and $N = 397$), we examined whether activating people's creativity strengthens their creative confidence. Participants completed the Alternate Uses Task (AUT) under either the "be creative" or "be fluent" conditions and responded to the measure of creative confidence. Those encouraged to "be creative" generated much more creative ideas (Study 1: $d = 1.48$, Study 2: $d = 1.68$), and the creativity of generated ideas mediated the effect of condition on creative confidence. At the same time, the effects were complex and moderated by participants' ability to accurately assess their ideas. People whose creativity was experimentally activated and who were metacognitively accurate were also more convinced about their creativity than those in the "be fluent" condition or those unable to appropriately recognize the originality of their ideas. Overall, both experiments highlight the relevance of cognitive and metacognitive factors for creative confidence.

Keywords: creative confidence; divergent thinking; metacognition

How Cognition and Metacognition Interact in Explaining Creative Confidence

Confidence beliefs drive people's engagement and help them achieve success (Bandura, 1997), including creative outcomes (Tierney & Farmer, 2002). Indeed, without believing in one's potential to succeed, a person is unlikely to try out, invest time, and flourish in any creative domain (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019). Hence, creative confidence, the "I can" conviction related to creative tasks and activities, explains differences in invested effort (Puente-Diaz & Arroyo, 2018), cognitive processes (Redifer et al., 2021), self-regulatory strategies used (Zielińska et al., 2024), and reactions to failures and setbacks (Han et al., 2022).

Still, however, little is known about how creative confidence is shaped and developed (Zandi et al., 2025). Sociocognitive theory (Bandura, 1997) proposes four such foundational building blocks. These are previous successes (mastery experiences), modeling and observing others (vicarious experiences), positive feedback (social persuasion), and physiological reactions. Creative Behavior as Agentic Action model (CBAA) (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019) adds creative potential to plausible sources of creative confidence. Creative potential can be understood as a set of observable indicators predictive of creative behavior, with divergent thinking among the most widely recognized cognitive predictors (Runco & Acar, 2012). According to CBAA, creative confidence is shaped by creative potential, and it further mediates the links between potential and behavior. Yet, while the results of correlational studies are usually in line with this reasoning (see Haase et al., 2018, for a meta-analysis), causal inferences require experimental or longitudinal designs, which were rarely used previously.

This article takes a step in this direction. In two preregistered experiments, we investigate how activating people's creative thinking translates into their creative

confidence. We additionally explore the role of people's ability to recognize their more-versus-less creative ideas (i.e., metacognitive accuracy) in this process. Hence, we explore and integrate the interplay between cognitive (divergent thinking) and metacognitive (accuracy) elements in explaining people's creative confidence.

Cognitive and Metacognitive Sources of Creative Confidence

Creative confidence reflects an individual's self-perceived ability to generate creative ideas and take effective actions (Karwowski et al., 2019a). Usually operationalized as either more dynamic and task-specific creative self-efficacy or more stable, trait-like creative self-concept (Beghetto & Karwowski, 2017; see also Marsh et al., 2019 for a discussion), confidence¹ was repeatedly linked to creativity, with somehow weaker links with divergent thinking (e.g., Puente-Diaz & Arroyo, 2017), and robust associations in the case of creative activity (e.g., Hong et al., 2014), real-life achievement (e.g., Zielińska et al., 2025) or innovative behavior (e.g., Hsu et al., 2011). Notably, confidence and performance are reciprocally related: believing in one's creativity—assuming this belief is at least moderately accurate (see Beghetto & Karwowski, 2025 for a discussion)—can lead to improved performance, a sort of *I believe, therefore I achieve* effect, as demonstrated in the educational psychology works (Talsma et al., 2018). At the same time, however, creative potential appears to be foundational to confidence, a phenomenon recently called the *abilities-shape-confidence effect* (Wiśniewska & Karwowski, 2026).

Yet, although more creative individuals are, on average, more confident in their abilities and skills (Haase et al., 2018; Lebuda & Csikszentmihalyi, 2017), an open question remains how their confidence is built and shaped. As mentioned, one possible source of

¹ For a detailed discussion of how *creative confidence* relates to *creative self-efficacy*, we refer interested readers to Beghetto & Karwowski (2025).

confidence is potential itself. There are at least two reasons to expect a causal link here, and although both are indirect, they warrant a brief discussion.

First, given that confidence arises from previous successes (Bandura, 1997; i.e., creative achievement in the case of creativity) and achievement is driven by creative potential (Benedek, 2024; Jauk et al., 2014; Said-Metwaly et al., 2022), people who are more creatively skilled have more reasons to believe in themselves. Two mechanisms are likely at play here: mastery experiences and social persuasion. Mastery experiences rely on previous successes, which provide individuals with arguments that they can excel in creative pursuits, just as they have in the past. Social persuasion refers to feedback from various sources (Bandura, 1997), including parents and teachers (Beghetto, 2006; Karwowski et al., 2015; Pugsley & Acar, 2020), as well as broader audiences evaluating a person's creativity (Liao et al., 2021), which further strengthens the "I can" conviction.

The second reason is metacognitive in nature. Creative people tend to be doubly skilled, not only able to generate original and meaningful ideas but also to recognize them properly (Silvia, 2008). More recent literature confirms that a link between the two exists, albeit modest in strength (Guo et al., 2022; Lebuda & Benedek, 2025), and that its magnitude varies depending on the methodology used (Guo et al., 2022). Hence, even if people's creative confidence is shaped by their potential, metacognitive skills may qualify this relationship. Here, we posit that metacognitive accuracy strengthens the link between potential and confidence, with robust associations between the two being unlikely if people cannot recognize whether their ideas or solutions are or are not creative.

Notably, recognizing and assessing ideas accurately is not straightforward (Berg, 2019; Puente-Díaz et al., 2021; Sidi et al., 2020). Person-centered analyses have identified various profiles or types of individuals, including underconfident, accurate, and

overconfident profiles (Karwowski et al., 2019a), as well as underestimating, overestimating, and unskilled but aware groups (Urban & Urban, 2021). Importantly, those with limited creative metacognition may find it particularly challenging to demonstrate elevated levels of creativity (Silvia, 2008). Accuracy, a key metacognitive component, might even serve as a necessary condition for creative performance (Urban & Urban, 2023). Indeed, failing to accurately assess one's strengths and weaknesses makes monitoring the process difficult, resulting in faulty resource allocation and worse effects (Brannick et al., 2005; Thompson et al., 2011).

Based on the current discussion, we hypothesize that when people's creative potential is activated, e.g., experimentally—as in the studies reported in this article—their creative confidence is boosted compared to the control condition. Moreover, and somehow more technically, activated potential (operationalized as increased creative performance) is hypothesized to mediate the link between the condition (experimental vs. control) and confidence measured afterward. Before testing those predictions in two preregistered experiments, we briefly discuss some vital nuances observed in recent theorizing and measurement of creative confidence.

On Malleability of Creative Confidence

The last three decades in creativity literature have witnessed a rising interest in people's convictions about their creative potential, analyzed under the broad umbrella of creative self-beliefs (see Karwowski et al., 2019b for a discussion). At the time of revising this article (December 22nd, 2025), Google Scholar returns more than 20,000 sources (25 200) for “creative self-efficacy,” 1340 for “creative self-concept,” 8140 for “creative confidence,” 1300 for “creative personal identity” (and additional 2230 for “creative role identity”), and

6880 for “creative mindset.” In short, self-beliefs have become a key area of research in the field.

Given this richness, it is no surprise that studies differ in operationalizing creative self-beliefs and their hypothesized role. While some research uses them as predictors (Lebuda et al., 2021; Simmons et al., 2014), others treat self-beliefs as outcomes (Mathisen & Bronnick, 2009; Tierney & Farmer, 2002), mediators (Gong et al., 2009; Royston & Reiter-Palmon, 2019), or moderators (Malik et al., 2015) of the associations between other variables. As per measurement, some studies rely on single items (Batey et al., 2010) (sometimes with denser, slider-like response scales, Benedek et al., 2025), while others apply very short (usually 3-item) instruments (Tierney & Farmer, 2002). There are also more elaborate measures that cover specific constructs (Karwowski et al., 2018) or domain-specific creative self-beliefs (Kaufman & Baer, 2004; Kaufman, 2012). Notably, with few exceptions (Karwowski et al., 2019a), the research focus is on static, stable characteristics akin to traits (Lebuda et al., 2021).

If creative confidence is relatively stable, one might doubt whether a brief activation of creative thinking would affect its level. Still, there are arguments to expect such changes. We see at least five reasons why such activation of creative potential could matter for creative confidence.

First, creative confidence is theorized as a surface personality characteristic (Lebuda et al., 2021; Lebuda, 2025) rather than a core trait. Surface personality characteristics are malleable and more sensitive to situational influences than core traits (Kandler et al., 2014), emerging through the interaction of core characteristics and experiences (McCrae, 2009). Empirical evidence further supports this notion by showing that creative confidence changes in response to creativity training (Mathisen & Bronnick, 2009), varies as a function of

measurement order (Czerwonka & Karwowski, 2018), and is influenced by self-regulatory prompts (Zielińska & Karwowski, 2025). Thus, the view that creative confidence can be shaped is supported by both theoretical arguments and empirical findings.

Second, while creative experiences are co-shaping creative confidence, individuals differ in the extent of their prior creative endeavors. Frequent behaviors that allow for ability inferences can improve self-concept clarity (Light & Visser, 2012). Consequently, (un)familiarity with a domain may qualify stability of creative confidence—those with more extensive creative experience are likely to hold more stable self-beliefs than those less experienced. In other words, individuals with few past creative encounters may be more reactive to a creative task, using their immediate performance as a basis for inferring their creative ability in the absence of stronger cues.

The third argument is phenomenological and relates to a person's interpretation of the situation. Someone interpreting the test situation as informative and meaningful might use it to calibrate their self-perception. Suppose you were asked to provide creative responses to the task, and you found your responses highly creative. Why shouldn't it empower your agency and boost confidence? However, the contrary is true when you perceive the task as superficial and unrelated to what you perceive as "real creativity." In such a case, it is rather unlikely that performance in, let's say, divergent thinking tasks will matter for people's self-perception as more or less creative.

The fourth—albeit related to the former—argument is metacognitive. There are people who, for various reasons—such as intelligence (Benedek et al., 2016), limited evaluative skills (Guo et al., 2022), or specific personality factors (Ceh et al., 2022)—tend to be less accurate in assessing their task performance. If someone's responses are obvious but self-misperceived as original, or if they are highly original but self-underappreciated (see

Karwowski et al., 2019a), chances are that experimentally activated creative potential will not inform creative confidence, or this effect will be substantially smaller. That is because the person does not associate their creative confidence with the actual value of their performance, but with a misperceived one. Thus, metacognitive accuracy is hypothesized to moderate the relationship between activated creative potential and creative confidence.

The fifth and final argument has methodological roots. Although creative confidence measures refer to relatively stable characteristics, their measurement might be more or less contextualized. Typically, when self-report instruments are used, the measurement is decontextualized, as people are asked to report how they usually behave or how they perceive themselves in general. Under such conditions, participants likely draw on a wide range of past situations and differing contexts when responding to each item, which may increase within-person inconsistency (Li et al., 2024). Contextualization, by contrast, involves anchoring a trait-oriented variable within a specific situation or environment (Schlotzhauer et al., 2025). Accumulating evidence suggests that such methodological procedure can enhance predictive validity by reducing ambiguity in self-evaluation, even when assessing relatively stable, trait-like constructs (Swift & Peterson, 2019; Shaffer & Postlethwaite, 2012). Importantly, the provided frame of reference does not shift the measure toward a state-like construct but situates self-assessment within a meaningful context that remains related to a more general measure (Dunlop, 2015). So what if creative confidence is measured in a trait-like way, but the measurement is contextualized around the specific task? What if instead of providing people with items such as “I can trust my creative abilities” (decontextualized), the researcher would present them with a statement like “When thinking of the ideas I just came up with [in the just finished task], I feel I can trust my

creative abilities” (contextualized). Would such measured creative confidence be more susceptible to change due to activated creative potential? We explore this reasoning below.

The Present Studies

This investigation builds on the classic “be creative” instruction effect (Harrington, 1975; Chen et al., 2005) to activate creative thinking. Abundant evidence indicates that the instruction participants receive impacts their performance and outcomes (Harrington, 1975; Chen et al., 2005; Nusbaum et al., 2014; Wei et al., 2024). Typically, two main instruction designs are employed in the Alternate Uses Task (AUT, Guilford, 1967): “be fluent” and “be creative” (Nusbaum et al., 2014; Forthmann et al., 2016). The “be creative” instruction yields more original and creative responses (Wei et al., 2024), presumably because it activates more effortful and controlled processes (Nusbaum et al., 2014; Forthmann et al., 2016). The “be fluent” condition activates memory retrieval strategies (Nusbaum et al., 2014) that—although vital for creativity (Beaty & Silvia, 2012; Kenett et al., 2014)—usually result in more repetitive and predictable ideas (Gonthier & Besançon, 2024).

We conducted two studies, each employing a divergent thinking task with participants randomly assigned to either the “be creative” or “be fluent” condition. Study 1 aimed to examine whether this manipulation would “boost” creative thinking in half of the sample and whether this activation—reflected in the hypothesized higher creative performance—informs participants’ creative confidence (H1). We additionally hypothesized that creative performance mediates the relationship between the condition and creative confidence (H1a). Study 2 aimed primarily to determine the generalizability of our findings. It extended Study 1 by incorporating a contextualized measure of creative confidence. Accordingly, Study 2 enabled a comparison of the generalizability of the effects obtained: decontextualized in Study 1 and contextualized in Study 2. We expected the mediational

pathway of condition – performance – confidence to be qualified by participants' metacognitive accuracy. Thus, we hypothesized a moderated mediation, with ideas' creativity mediating the relationship between condition and creative confidence, where path b (idea creativity → creative confidence) and the whole mediation is further moderated by creative metacognitive accuracy (H1b) (see Figure 1).

Together, these two studies allow us to test the theorized causal role of creative performance in creative confidence formation. What is more, we examine the direct and indirect effects of instructional task framing on creative confidence, as well as the qualifying role of creative metacognitive accuracy. The analyses extend across two samples of different nationalities, with the nuanced distinction between decontextualized and contextualized measures of creative confidence.

Figure 1

Conceptual Diagram of the Moderated Mediation Model Used in Two Studies

Note. CM Accuracy = Creative Metacognitive Accuracy.

Study 1

Method

Participants. Participants ($N = 301$) were Polish adults recruited through the Prolific research panel. The mean age in the sample was 27.60 years ($SD = 7.27$; range 18-53 years; 49% female). All participants provided informed consent and were remunerated. Participants needed to provide valid responses to the AUT task and pass the attention check to be included in the sample. There were no exclusions from the present sample.

Measures

Idea Creativity. Participants solved the AUT (Guilford, 1967), providing unusual uses for a brick. This task had no time limit; however, at least 3 responses were required, and a maximum of 20 was allowed. Eight trained student assistants rated the creativity of responses on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 = *not creative at all* to 5 = *very creative*. Raters were divided into two groups. Each idea was rated by 4 judges and their scores were averaged—inter-rater reliability was good: in the first group, $ICC(3, k) = .85$, and in the second $ICC(3, k) = .87$. For enhanced interpretability some graphs and descriptives are presented on the original scale in which averaged creativity ratings were ranging from 1.08 to 3.65 ($M = 2.08$; $SD = 0.52$) in the sample. Before the analyses, however, we standardized each expert's ratings at the idea level to control for judges' severity (Long & Pang, 2015). The standardized creativity ratings of all ideas provided by a participant were averaged, and at the individual level, they ranged from -1.08 to 1.61 ($M = -0.02$, $SD = 0.54$). Non-standardized and standardized measures were nearly perfectly correlated ($r = .99$, $p < .001$).

Creative Confidence. Creative confidence was measured using the revised Short Scale of Creative Self (SSCS; Karwowski et al., 2018; Zielińska et al., 2022). This scale consists of 18 items, where 9 constitute the creative confidence subscale (e.g., "I am sure I can deal

with problems requiring creative thinking," $\alpha = .85$) and the remaining 9 compose the creative centrality subscale (e.g., "My creativity is important for who I am," $\alpha = .88$). There is one negative statement in each subscale used to identify potential string response patterns and careless responding (Curran, 2016). We only analyzed the confidence scale in the current study. Participants used a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *definitely not*, 5 = *definitely yes*). The mean of confidence items was used as a creative confidence metric.

Post-task Self-evaluation. Post-task self-evaluation refers to participants' assessments of the creativity of their own ideas. In this study, it was used to operationalize creative metacognitive accuracy, that is, the degree to which individuals' self-evaluations correspond to the objective scoring of their creative performance. Post-task self-evaluation was measured using two items: a self-evaluation judgment and a comparison judgment (as suggested in Karwowski et al., 2019a; Urban & Urban, 2021), presented immediately after the AUT. Participants assessed the overall originality of their ideas, and their relative originality compared to others, using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *definitely not original/less original*, 5 = *definitely original/more original*). The two scores were then averaged to create a single self-evaluation measure. The obtained reliability was acceptable ($\alpha = .73$), an equivalent of high inter-item correlations ($r = .57, p < .001$).

Creative Metacognitive Accuracy (CMA). The CMA was calculated as the squared difference between the percentile ranks of the post-task self-evaluation and the AUT scores, subtracted from 1 (similar to Urban & Urban, 2023). CMA scores in our study ranged from 0.14 to 1.00 ($M = 0.89, SD = 0.15$). Due to the inversion (1–squared difference), higher CMA values indicate greater accuracy—that is, a closer alignment between self-assessment and the objective creativity score. The distribution slightly deviated from normal, with negatively skewed scores (skewness = -2.28).

Procedure

This study was preregistered (<https://aspredicted.org/jngn-yx4x.pdf>) and obtained ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board at *masked for peer review*. It was conducted online using the PsyToolkit platform (Stoet, 2010, 2017) and distributed through the Prolific research panel. After providing basic demographic data, participants were randomly assigned to one of two instruction conditions: “be creative” ($N = 145$) or “be fluent” ($N = 156$). The “be creative” condition emphasized the creativity of solutions, whereas the “be fluent” condition underlined the quantity. Participants completed the AUT and proceeded to a post-task self-evaluation and SSCS. All instruments were administered in Polish.

Analytical Approach

The analyses were performed using R 4.4.2 (R Core Team, 2024). The data with analyses are openly available at the Open Science Framework (OSF) repository:

https://osf.io/4sxce/?view_only=704e5c9309014546b7d1d1cd00e3ecc1. We began our analyses with correlations and descriptive statistics to examine the basic relationships between variables and their characteristics. Then, we moved to preregistered analyses. All the preregistered effects were analyzed with one-tailed statistical tests (see Hales, 2024; 90% confidence intervals were applied). Accordingly, given our preregistered directional hypotheses, we conducted a one-tailed Welch’s t-test to examine whether creativity was higher in the “be creative” than in the “be fluent” condition. We continued analyses with a one-tailed t-test to compare creative confidence levels across conditions. Then, we run a mediation analysis using 5,000 bootstrap samples with lavaan (Rosseel, 2012) to estimate the indirect effect of condition on idea creativity and creative confidence. Afterward, we moved to exploratory, non-preregistered analyses, all of which used 95% confidence intervals (i.e., two-tailed tests). Specifically, we ran a moderated mediation, again using

lavaan (Rosseel, 2012), to examine whether CMA moderates the indirect pathway from condition to creative confidence via idea creativity (see Figure 1). We emphasize that while the moderated mediation was not preregistered for Study 1, it was preregistered for Study 2 (see below). In our results, we report both path b moderation effects and overall mediation effect sizes across levels of the moderator. In all analyses, the magnitude of effect sizes was interpreted following statistical guidelines (for correlations—Gignac & Szodorai, 2016; for Cohen’s *d*—Cohen, 1988).

Preregistration and Deviations

With one exception, all analyses followed the preregistered plan. Specifically, although post-task self-evaluation (labeled in preregistration as task-related creative confidence) was initially intended to be examined as an outcome, we did not retain it in that role. Instead, in the interest of conceptual clarity and in line with the suggestions of anonymous reviewers, we used it only to establish an index of metacognitive accuracy. We acknowledge that, while examining whether our manipulation influenced post-task self-evaluation (it actually did) might be of interest to some readers, we also recognize that treating it as another dependent variable introduces conceptual ambiguity. Therefore, we invite scholars interested in the effects of the “be creative” vs. “be fluent” instruction on post-task self-assessment to reanalyze our openly available data from both experiments.

Results

Descriptive statistics and correlations are displayed separately for conditions in Table 1 (upper part). Correlation analysis is two-tailed, with the significance level set at $p \leq .05$. Post-task self-evaluation and creative confidence were significantly related in both the “be fluent” ($r = .31, p < .001$) and “be creative” ($r = .47, p < .001$) conditions. Idea creativity was moderately to strongly related to post-task self-evaluation (“be creative,” $r = .26, p = .001$;

“be fluent,” $r = .33, p < .001$), but not to creative confidence (“be creative,” $r = .07, p = .418$; “be fluent,” $r = .15, p = .063$). Finally, while CMA was linked to creative confidence among participants prompted to be creative while working on the task ($r = .26, p = .002$), it was unrelated among those instructed to be fluent ($r = -.06, p = .445$).

At first glance, the links between CMA and both idea creativity and post-task self-evaluation suggest intriguing, oppositely signed relationships across conditions (see Table 1). However, since the CMA metric is derived from these two variables, such associations reflect rather spurious self-correlations. Moreover, lower levels of CMA can indicate either over- or underestimation of one’s creativity, thus further complicating interpretation (see SOM for a more thorough examination of under- and overestimation using the bias index).

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics and Correlations Between Variables of Studies 1-2

Study	Group	Variable	M	SD	2	3	4
S1	Be creative (N = 145)	1: Idea creativity	2.40	0.46	.26**	.07	-.29***
		2: Post-task self-evaluation	2.93	0.80		.47***	.51***
		3: Creative confidence	3.36	0.65			.26**
		4: CMA	0.89	0.15			
	Be fluent (N = 156)	1: Idea creativity	1.78	0.38	.33***	.15	.05
		2: Post-task self-evaluation	2.63	0.77		.31***	-.35***
		3: Creative confidence	3.25	0.67			-.06
		4: CMA	0.89	0.14			
S2	Be creative (N = 204)	1: Idea creativity	2.40	0.43	.24***	.16*	-.04
		2: Post-task self-evaluation	3.00	0.84		.46***	.57***
		3: Creative confidence	2.92	0.79			.37***
		4: CMA	0.88	0.15			
	Be fluent (N=193)	1: Idea creativity	1.74	0.35	.33***	.35***	.19*
		2: Post-task self-evaluation	2.71	0.96		.77***	-.52***

3: Creative confidence	2.78	0.88	-.33***
4: CMA	0.89	0.16	

Note. Study 1: $N = 301$, Study 2: $N = 397$, CMA = creative metacognitive accuracy

* $p \leq .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Preregistered Analyses

An independent samples (one-tailed) t-test showed statistically significant between-group differences in idea creativity with a very large effect size, $t(276.92) = 12.71$, $p < .001$, $d = 1.48$, an equivalent of 93% of the “be creative” group scoring higher than the average participant in the “be fluent” group. Participants completing the task with the “be creative” instruction generated more creative ideas ($M = 2.40$, $SD = 0.46$) than those providing responses under the “be fluent” instruction ($M = 1.78$, $SD = 0.38$).

There were no significant differences in creative confidence, $t(299) = 1.41$; $p = .079$; $d = 0.16$. Thus, instruction manipulation did not directly affect creative confidence.

Figure 2

Differences Between Conditions Across Two Studies. For Each Study—Top Panel: Idea Creativity, Bottom Panel: Creative Confidence

Note. Effect sizes in bold represent Cohen's *d* for significant differences between groups.

The mediation model was estimated next (Figure 3), with creative confidence regressed on idea creativity (the mediator) and condition (independent variable). The indirect effect was significant, $b = 0.11$, 90% CI: 0.02, 0.20. The direct effect was non-significant after the mediator was incorporated into the model (see Figure 3).

Figure 3

The Relationship between Condition (“Be fluent” vs. “Be creative”) and Creative Confidence as Mediated by Idea Creativity in Two Studies

Note. Indirect effects are unstandardized, with 90% confidence intervals shown in the brackets. The remaining coefficients are standardized regression weights (β). The upper panel illustrates the direct relationship between the predictor and the outcome, without accounting for the mediator (which also represents the total effect in simple mediation—see Hayes, 2018). Significant effects are bolded. All preregistered effects were tested with one-tailed tests.

* $p \leq .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Exploratory (Non-Preregistered) Analyses

We examined whether metacognitive accuracy moderates the relationship between idea creativity and creative confidence. This was indeed the case (see Table 2). We observed the moderated mediation ($b = 0.91$, 95% CI: 0.47, 1.41), indicating that activating creative

thinking translated via idea creativity into creative confidence (conditional indirect effects) more substantially among those participants who were accurate in assessing their creativity (+1SD, $b = 0.28$, 95% CI: 0.17, 0.41) compared to moderately accurate participants ($b = 0.15$, 95% CI: 0.06, 0.26) and those unable to properly recognize originality of their ideas (−1SD; $b = 0.01$, 95% CI: −0.11, 0.14), among whom the conditional indirect effect was no longer significant. The moderation was evident both at the level of the b path (idea creativity → creative confidence; see Figure 4) and in the overall mediated effect (see Figure 5). At least moderate creative metacognitive accuracy was needed for the relationship between idea creativity and creative confidence to appear.

Table 2

A Summary of Moderated Mediation Models with Creative Confidence as a Dependent Variable, Condition as an Independent Variable, and Idea Creativity as a Mediator (Studies 1 and 2)

Predictors	Study 1		Study 2	
	M: Idea Creativity	DV: Creative Confidence	M: Idea Creativity	DV: Creative Confidence
Condition (0 = be fluent, 1 = be creative)	$d = 1.19^{***}$ (0.03)	$d = -0.01$ (0.07)	$d = 1.29^{***}$ (0.03)	$d = -0.20$ (0.06)*
CMA		$\beta = .07$ (.06)		$\beta = .07$ (.05)
Idea creativity		$\beta = .19^{**}$ (.06)		$\beta = .33^{***}$ (.06)
Idea creativity x CMA		$\beta = .23^{***}$ (.06)		$\beta = .45^{***}$ (.04)
R^2	.35	.09	.42	.27
ΔR^2	—	.07	—	.21
Index of Moderated Mediation	0.91 [0.47, 1.41]		2.68 [2.21, 3.13]	

Note. Study 1: $N = 301$. Study 2: $N = 397$. Values in brackets represent bootstrap-corrected confidence intervals: 95% for Study 1 and 90% for Study 2, reflecting exploratory vs. preregistered directional analysis. Standard errors are shown in parentheses. d represents the standardized coefficient estimated using the *std.nox* option in *lavaan* (R 4.4.2), comparable to Cohen’s d , but based on the total standard deviation of the outcome variable. ΔR^2 represents the difference between the R^2 of the moderated and simple mediation. M = mediator; DV = dependent variable; CMA = creative metacognitive accuracy.

* $p \leq .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Figure 4

The Relationship Between Idea Creativity and Creative Confidence (Path B) on Three Levels of the Moderator (CMA) Across Study 1(Left) and Study 2 (Right)

Note. The figure shows raw data (not modeled) with levels of a moderator based on a tertile division into low, moderate, and high accuracy groups.

Figure 5

Mediation Effect Sizes by Moderator Levels (CMA) Across Two Studies—Conditional Indirect Effects

Note. Bootstrap-corrected confidence intervals: 95% for Study 1 and 90% for Study 2.

Discussion

In Study 1, we activated participants' creative thinking using the "be creative" instruction. Our preregistered hypotheses predicted that boosted creativity would translate into creative confidence. In addition, we performed an exploratory moderated mediation analysis with metacognitive accuracy serving as a moderator of the indirect effect in creative confidence.

The results of Study 1 largely aligned with our preregistered hypotheses. Participants assigned to the "be creative" instruction generated more creative ideas (as expected based on the "be creative" effect; see Forthmann et al., 2016), but the groups did not differ in terms of creative confidence. Given the trait-like nature of this characteristic, it is reasonable to expect it to be less susceptible to immediate, situational changes (Zandi et al., 2025).

However, we would discourage dismissing potential effects on creative confidence too quickly. As a reminder, our instructional manipulation was aimed at boosting creative thinking to assess how creativity activation affects confidence. And while the manipulation itself did not, on average, shift participants' confidence beliefs (compared to the control group), our preregistered mediation analyses suggested a plausible indirect mechanism at play. Specifically, participants encouraged to think creatively generated more creative ideas, and this expression of creative potential, in turn, led to higher creative confidence. In other words, the boost in creative confidence arose not from the instructional framing alone, but through participants' experience of the task. In our study, participants executed the task differently depending on the assigned condition, and they used their recent performance as a basis for evaluating their creative abilities. Thus, the instruction shaped confidence indirectly—by influencing how individuals perform in the task. In sum, the abilities-shape-confidence effect (Wiśniewska & Karwowski, 2026) emerges as a plausible mechanism, supporting the previously theorized link between creative potential and creative agency (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019).

Our exploratory analyses further revealed conditions under which this mechanism operates. One would assume that how people perceive their creative ability in a specific task context depends not only on their performance but also on whether their self-assessment of this performance is accurate (Karwowski et al., 2020). Indeed, Study 1 showed that among people who could recognize how well or poorly they performed in the creativity task, the indirect effect of condition (via idea creativity) on creative confidence was significantly stronger than among those unable to accurately assess the creativity of their ideas. The association between idea creativity and creative confidence (path b) was stronger among people who made more accurate self-assessments, suggesting that creative metacognitive

accuracy plays a role in shaping creative confidence. In essence, activating creativity mattered for creative confidence, but only among individuals who were at least moderately accurate in recognizing the creativity of their ideas. Metacognitive processes are considered necessary for optimal creative performance (Urban & Urban, 2023) as they enable people to navigate the process effectively (Thompson et al., 2011). Our findings suggest that accuracy also helps calibrate creative confidence following recent expression of creative abilities.

Yet, were people whose creativity had been activated also more accurate?

Interestingly, the experimental conditions did not differ in terms of creative metacognitive accuracy—although creative abilities were activated in one group, this did not increase accuracy. This expands previous research on the “double skills” of creative people (Silvia, 2008; Ceh et al., 2022) by showing that brief creative thinking activation is not necessarily accompanied by more accurate self-assessment. Instead, metacognitive accuracy may rely on a range of more stable individual differences—such as long-term experience in creative activities, openness, and intelligence (Benedek et al., 2016; Ceh et al., 2022; Silvia, 2008).

Study 1 provides experimental evidence for the role of creative ability in shaping creative confidence. By manipulating instructions, we were able to activate creative thinking in one group, which, in turn, led to higher idea creativity and an increase in participants’ creative confidence. The indirect effect on creative confidence suggested that expressed creative ability informs individuals’ creative self-perception. This finding aligns well with previous theorizing (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019) and extends it by identifying the moderating role of creative metacognitive accuracy.

Although promising, these results warrant further research to replicate the key findings and to more fully validate exploratory patterns (i.e., moderated mediation effects). While we recognize that the indirect effect of creativity activation on creative confidence is

theoretically meaningful and was expected *a priori*, the lack of a significant total effect (i.e., between-condition differences) might be considered problematic (but see the discussion in Hayes, 2022, for the limitation associated with focusing on non-significant direct or total effects in lights or presence of hypothesized indirect effect). One possible explanation for the null direct effect is the decontextualized nature of the creative confidence measure, which may have led to perceptions that were somewhat detached from participants' situational experiences. However, such general confidence beliefs can still be anchored to the task at hand and, thus, be more susceptible to change in experimental settings. Therefore, Study 2 sought to more effectively contextualize creative confidence measurement, replicate the core findings of Study 1, and further examine the nuanced dynamics of creative confidence.

Study 2

The second preregistered experiment (<https://aspredicted.org/b548-nphz.pdf>) aimed to replicate Study 1's findings while addressing its limitations. More specifically, Study 2 employed a slightly reframed, contextualized creative confidence measurement. Previous studies on core personal characteristics successfully implemented contextualization, increasing predictive validity without compromising trait specificity (e.g., Swift & Peterson, 2019; Shaffer & Postlethwaite, 2012). In Study 2, we attempted to contextualize creative confidence items by linking them directly to the divergent thinking task people solved. Our goal with this approach was to prompt participants to use their recent creative performance as a reference point for evaluating their general creative ability, thereby bridging situational experience and broader self-beliefs. What remained unchanged was the overall design; again, by activating creativity with the "be creative" instruction, we expected an increase in

participants' creative confidence, and hypothesized that metacognitive accuracy would further moderate the effect of idea creativity on creative confidence.

Method

Participants

Participants ($N = 397$) were English speakers recruited through the Prolific research panel. The mean age in the sample was 39.30 years ($SD = 13.50$; range 18-79 years; 49% female). All participants provided informed consent and received remuneration for their contribution. In line with our preregistration, participants were included if they provided valid responses in the AUT task and did not exhibit a string response pattern on the SSCS scale. There were no exclusions based on the assumed criteria.

Measures

Idea Creativity. Participants solved the AUT for a brick with the exact instructions as in Study 1. Creativity ratings were obtained following the previously described procedure from Study 1. The same two groups of raters as in Study 1 assessed idea creativity and obtained good inter-rater reliability: $ICC(3, k) = .88$ in the first group of raters and $ICC(3, k) = .82$ in the second. Again, for enhanced interpretability, figures and descriptives use the non-standardized averaged creativity ratings, which ranged from 1.00 to 3.92 ($M = 2.08$; $SD = 0.51$) in the present sample. Yet, for the analyses, we standardized each rating to account for individual raters' severity (Long & Pang, 2015). The averaged standardized creativity scores ranged from -1.18 to 1.96 ($M = -0.03$; $SD = 0.56$). The metrics derived from standardized and unstandardized scores were almost perfectly correlated ($r = .99$, $p < .001$).

Creative Confidence. As in Study 1, we used the revised Short Scale of Creative Self (SSCS; Karwowski et al., 2018; Zielińska et al., 2022), but with modifications to the item wording. As we wanted participants to reflect on their creativity based on the divergent

thinking performance, we excluded items that did not fit the dynamic setup of the study (e.g., “I was the most imaginative child in preschool and school”) and rephrased the remaining items to suit the task context (e.g., “Considering my performance in the previous task, I think I am good at proposing original solutions to problems.”). Ultimately, we used seven items to measure creative confidence ($\alpha = .89$). The negatively phrased item was used solely as an attention check.

Post-task Self-evaluation. Post-task self-evaluation was measured in the same way as in Study 1. The obtained reliability was acceptable ($\alpha = .74$), an equivalent of $r = .61$, $p < .001$.

CMA. Creative metacognitive accuracy was calculated as in Study 1. Scores ranged from 0.17 to 1.00 ($M = 0.89$, $SD = 0.15$), with higher scores indicating greater accuracy. The distribution showed an acceptable level of normality (skewness = -2.01 ; see West et al., 1995).

Procedure

This study was conducted online using PsyToolkit (Stoet, 2010, 2017) and distributed through the Prolific research panel. Participants were randomly assigned to one of the instruction conditions: “be fluent” ($N = 193$) and “be creative” ($N = 204$). All instruments were administered in English.

Analytical Approach

The analyses were performed using R 4.4.2 (R Core Team, 2024). The data with analyses are available at the Open Science Framework (OSF) repository:

https://osf.io/4sxce/?view_only=704e5c9309014546b7d1d1cd00e3ecc1. The analytical

procedures followed those in Study 1. All the preregistered effects were analyzed with one-tailed statistical tests (i.e., 90% confidence intervals applied).

Results

Descriptive statistics and correlations between Study 2 variables are presented in Table 1 (lower part). Correlation analysis is two-tailed, with the significance level set at $p \leq .05$. Post-task self-evaluation and creative confidence were robustly linked in the “be creative” group ($r = .46, p < .001$) and even more strongly in the “be fluent” group ($r = .77, p < .001$). Idea creativity was moderately to highly correlated with post-task self-evaluation ($r = .24, p < .001$ in “be creative”; $r = .33, p < .001$ in “be fluent”); the correlation with creative confidence was significant but relatively small in the “be creative” condition ($r = .16, p = .027$) and stronger in the “be fluent” group ($r = .35, p < .001$). Creative confidence was strongly and positively correlated with CMA in the “be creative” condition ($r = .37, p < .001$), whereas the link was oppositely signed in the “be fluent” condition ($r = -.33, p < .001$). See the SOM for exploration of the opposite accuracy patterns using the bias index measure.

Preregistered Analyses

An independent samples t-test demonstrated that idea creativity was higher in the “be creative” than in the “be fluent” condition, $t(382.26) = 16.82; p < .001$, with an even stronger effect size ($d = 1.68$) than in Study 1, indicating that 95% of the “be creative” group scored higher than the average member of the “be fluent” group (see Figure 2).

Creative confidence differed significantly between groups, $t(395) = 1.71; p = .044, d = 0.17$. Participants in the “be creative” condition ($M = 2.92, SD = 0.79$) reported higher creative confidence than those in the “be fluent” condition ($M = 2.78, SD = 0.88$).

As in Study 1, we examined whether the creativity of ideas mediates the relationship between condition and confidence (see Figure 3). It was indeed the case; the relationship between condition and creative confidence was mediated by ideas’ creativity (indirect effect: $b = 0.33, 90\% \text{ CI: } 0.21, 0.45$). Further, there was a significant negative direct effect of

condition on creative confidence ($\beta = -.12, p = .031$) when ideas' creativity was controlled, alongside a significant positive total effect ($\beta = .08, p = .050$).

Did creative metacognitive accuracy further moderate the observed patterns? For Study 2, we preregistered the moderated mediation model previously discovered in Study 1. The index of moderated mediation was significant, $b = 2.68$, 90% CI: 2.21, 3.13. Among highly accurate individuals, the relationship between condition and creative confidence as mediated by idea creativity was stronger, $b = 0.77$, 90% CI: 0.64, 0.90, than among moderately accurate individuals, $b = 0.36$, 90% CI: 0.25, 0.46; among inaccurate ($-1SD$) participants, the relationship became non-significant ($b = -0.06$, 90% CI: $-0.18, 0.07$; see Table 2 and Figures 5 and 6), fully replicating Study 1 findings. Therefore, greater accuracy strengthened the link between idea creativity and creative confidence, as well as the overall mediation. In contrast, idea creativity did not link to creative confidence among participants with low accuracy.

Discussion

Study 2 confirmed that activating creative thinking in experimental settings can enhance creative confidence when confidence is contextualized within the task. Our mediation model showed that activating creative thinking leads to higher confidence and that increased idea creativity is a plausible mechanism behind this change. Moreover, replicating Study 1 findings, Study 2 provided even stronger evidence for the role of metacognitive accuracy as a moderator of the relationship between activated creative potential and creative confidence.

By anchoring participants' creative self-perceptions more firmly in the task context, we were able to support the CBAA-derived assumption about the directional link between creative potential—here, activated through the experimental manipulation—and creative confidence (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019). Encouraging creative thinking in a simple yet

effective way (we emphasize the strong “be creative” effects; see Figure 2) led to higher confidence beliefs, as reflected in significant between-group differences in creative confidence. When examining the effect of instruction without accounting for the mediator, the effect sizes were similar across the two studies, although only Study 2 reached statistical significance. The larger sample size in Study 2 likely contributed to the detection of this effect of instructional manipulation on creative confidence, as observed in both the t-test and the total effect in the mediation model.

Study 2 also replicated the moderating effect of metacognitive accuracy on the association between condition (i.e., activated creativity) and creative confidence as mediated by idea creativity. The mediation effect was significant among individuals with moderate to high accuracy in recognizing their creativity. In contrast, those with low accuracy did not benefit from the confidence-boosting indirect effect of creative thinking activation. The link between creative confidence and idea creativity (path b) was conditioned on accuracy.

The observed moderating effects were larger than in Study 1, probably due to the contextualization of the creative confidence items. Contextualization has previously been found to be an effective method for increasing the predictive validity of instruments such as personality measures (see Swift & Peterson, 2019). A specified frame of reference encourages active reflection, reduces ambiguity, and reduces within-person inconsistency (Lievens et al., 2008). We found no differences in absolute accuracy between the two studies, $t(695) = 0.77, p = .441$, suggesting that the strengthened relationship between creative confidence and accuracy was probably driven by the contextualization of the creative confidence measure.

Overall, Study 2 strengthens the evidence for the role of creative ability in shaping creative confidence. It supports the hypothesized mediated relationship between condition (i.e., creativity activation), idea creativity, and creative confidence. Additionally, the consistent pattern of moderated mediation across studies underscores the importance of metacognition in this process. Hence, creative cognitive and metacognitive processes play an important role in shaping creative confidence. Lastly, we emphasize the core findings replicated across Polish-speaking (Study 1) and English-speaking participants (Study 2), which further speaks to the generalizability of the observed effects.

General Discussion

What makes people believe in their ability? Is it the praise they received in elementary school when solving a task in a new way? Or rather, a prize awarded for their artwork? Perhaps both? Does their confidence develop because people perform well across various creative challenges, or is it driven by a favorable comparison with others? As sociocognitive theory explains (Bandura, 1977), all these—and many others—factors contribute to people’s agency and confidence, including creative confidence. This study focused on the link between creative ability and creative confidence, assuming that people adjust their self-perception following performance (see Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019). In other words, the process and outcome of a creative task can serve as a gauge for assessing one’s creative ability. In this article, we experimentally tested this effect. At the same time, we explored the role of creative metacognition in forming creative confidence.

Creative Abilities as Drivers of Confidence

The two experiments presented in this article were inspired by the CBAA model, specifically its assumption that abilities drive confidence. This reasoning is challenging to test, yet the results provide initial support for the abilities-shape-confidence effect (see Wiśniewska &

Karwowski, 2026). Indeed, when people's creative abilities were activated by the "be creative" instruction, they provided more creative responses and felt more confident. CBAA framework posits that people calibrate their self-views based on their abilities. Creativity researchers have already demonstrated consistent, albeit modest, correlational links between divergent thinking performance and creative self-efficacy (Haase et al., 2018). Longitudinal evidence indicating that creative potential shapes creative confidence is also available (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019, Study 3). However, the causal influence of creative ability on confidence has not been experimentally tested to date.

To fill this gap, we examined how abilities shape self-perception by activating creative thinking with the "be creative" instruction effect. This activation proved highly effective, with effect sizes ($d = 1.48$ and $d = 1.68$ in Study 1 and Study 2, respectively) being even stronger than previously reported (see Wei et al., 2024, for a meta-analytical estimate of $d = 0.69$). Moreover, our results indicate that participants whose creative ability was activated were more confident in their creativity (H1; the direct effect of instruction was supported only in Study 2). We obtained significant indirect effects across both studies, showing that instruction had a substantial impact on idea creativity, which in turn further informed creative confidence (Study 1 and Study 2). Hence, the hypothesized mediation effect (H1a) was indeed obtained and replicated.

Notably, we found that the effect of activated creativity on creative confidence occurred primarily among people who were accurate in their self-assessment (H1b). No mediating effects were observed among those unable to accurately assess their idea creativity. There are, naturally, various potential explanations for being inaccurate while assessing one's performance. First, individuals may deem themselves highly creative or not based on their prior experiences and self-other appraisals, thereby being less prone to adjust

their assessments in response to brief situational cues, including AUT. Second, some participants may have limited experience with tasks similar to those used in our experiments (i.e., AUT; see van Broekhoven et al., 2022, for task exposure effects on accuracy). Consequently, they might struggle to recognize the creativity of their ideas (Silvia, 2008) or be unsure what constitutes a creative idea. Third, and related to the former, some individuals may hold a particular implicit theory of creativity (see Benedek et al., 2021), which can render their self-perceived creative confidence independent of AUT performance. Suppose someone believes that creativity equals art (Glăveanu, 2014), requires Big-C level achievements (Beghetto, 2010), or is an inherited trait (Karwowski, 2014). In that case, it is doubtful that activating their creativity through a simple, task-like creative challenge will shape self-perception. Fourth, some individual differences, such as openness or intelligence (Benedek et al., 2016; Ceh et al., 2022; Silvia, 2008), may further moderate accurate idea discernment.

The creativity literature shows that creative confidence is linked to individuals' creative abilities (Haase et al., 2018). We demonstrated that idea creativity in a divergent thinking task can serve as a reference for creative confidence judgments. This seems particularly promising, given that most people (unlike many creativity researchers) do not pay much attention to their creativity in everyday life (Silvia et al., 2012). Expressing creative potential across various tasks can enable them to infer their abilities, as in the current research. Following this reasoning, it is interesting to consider how the relationships among creative thinking, confidence, and accuracy unfold in creative professionals. With numerous past creative activities and achievements, one's creative confidence is likely more resistant to change, especially in reference to what can be considered a superficial and non-diagnostic

task. Thus, future studies should extend these mechanisms to pro-C level creative individuals.

The key hypotheses for this study might seem straightforward and intuitive: people who are encouraged to engage their creative thinking during a task—those who receive a “be creative” instruction—consider themselves more creative. A critical reader might even view the measurement of creative confidence in such a context as a mere manipulation check. However, our results show that the effects of activating creative thinking on people’s self-perception are far from obvious. While instruction-induced differences in creative performance were clear and substantial (ranging from $d = 1.48$ in Study 1 to $d = 1.68$ in Study 2), the effects on creative confidence were much smaller ($d = 0.16$ in Study 1, $d = 0.17$ in Study 2) and indirect. Indeed, the instructional cue to be creative enhanced self-perception by influencing performance. Put differently, it was the activated and effectively expressed creative thinking that boosted confidence, not sole compliance with the instruction.

The Role of Metacognitive Accuracy

Metacognition is intertwined with a creative process. It enables switching between convergent and divergent thinking (Rominger et al., 2022) and organizing adequate resource allocation (Thompson et al., 2011). Through metacognitive control and monitoring, people can determine whether to follow and elaborate on one idea or seek an alternative solution. Creative metacognitive accuracy is often operationalized as an alignment between subjective and objective creative measurement (Silvia, 2008; Kaufman et al., 2016). Creators evaluate their work when deciding which project is worth pursuing and which should be presented to the broader public. Laypeople also utilize the same monitoring across different domains (Kaufman et al., 2016), though to a lesser extent than professionals (Fayena-Tawil

et al., 2011). Importantly, as previously discussed, more creative individuals tend to be more accurate on average (Silvia, 2008; Ceh et al., 2022).

Our experiments demonstrated that accuracy moderates the relationship between activated creativity and creative confidence. High accuracy may seem beneficial in itself, as it increases the likelihood of optimal performance, provided that an individual is aware of the obstacles, requirements, and progress throughout the task (Sidi et al., 2020). Further, accuracy was found to be a necessary condition for higher creative performance (Urban & Urban, 2023). Additionally, it was argued that self-evaluation skills should be developed alongside creative thinking to achieve significant improvement in creative performance (Loneragan et al., 2004). In our study, absolute accuracy showed only weak and inconsistent associations with idea creativity (in Study 1: $r = -.12$, $p = .044$; in Study 2: $r = .04$, $p = .423$), suggesting that self-evaluation accuracy may stem from multiple more stable characteristics such as long-term engagement in activities, accumulated achievements (Mabe & West, 1982), or dispositional traits like openness and cognitive ability (Benedek et al., 2016; Ceh et al., 2022; Silvia, 2008). However, high and moderate levels of metacognitive accuracy appeared crucial for the transfer from idea creativity to creative confidence. These findings add nuance to prior work on the dual nature of competencies in creative individuals (Silvia, 2008; Ceh et al., 2022).

Limitations and Future Directions

Although this article reports two preregistered experiments—the second replicating and extending the first—our findings should be read with certain limitations in mind.

Conceptually, one such limitation concerns our reasoning about creative abilities. We inferred creative ability based on participants' divergent thinking performance. Yet, although divergent thinking is a vital mechanism underlying interindividual differences in creative

abilities, creativity is not reducible to divergent thinking (Runco & Acar, 2012). Moreover, performance in AUT depends not only on participants' ability (see Ford, 1992; Anderson, 1974), but also on other factors, such as mood (Vosburg, 1998), stress (Wang et al., 2019), and motivation (Wilken et al., 2020).

Another limitation of current experiments was that participants assessed the originality of their ideas at once (snapshot scoring; Runco & Mraz, 1992; Saretzki et al., 2024) rather than on an idea-by-idea basis. Although similar solutions were used previously (Shaw, 2021), we acknowledge that such measures may have been biased toward the best or worst solution or the first or last idea, thereby impairing accuracy. Future studies could investigate how various self-assessment paradigms impact the creative metacognitive accuracy index.

It is also worth acknowledging an apparent limitation of our index of creative metacognitive accuracy. Deriving both metacognitive accuracy and creative performance measures from the same task may lead to collinearity issues (Urban & Urban, 2023). Notably, however, in our study, creative metacognitive accuracy did not serve as a focal predictor or outcome of idea creativity; instead, it was tested as a moderator of the relationship between idea creativity and creative confidence. More importantly, collinearity was not a problem in our studies; creative metacognitive accuracy and idea creativity were only weakly correlated.

Another limitation of the present research concerns a difference in the operationalization of post-task self-evaluation and creative performance. Post-task self-evaluations were based on participants' perceived originality, while judges' ratings of creative performance focused on creativity. Yet, as originality is a necessary but not sufficient component of creativity (Runco & Jaeger, 2012), relying on participants' ratings of

originality rather than creativity may have reduced alignment between post-task self-evaluation (originality) and rated performance (creativity), potentially attenuating estimates of creative metacognitive accuracy.

Future studies could explore whether the observed effects persist when the “be creative” condition is juxtaposed with a more general instruction condition that does not underline the quantity of ideas. In fact, the “be fluent” condition might elicit memory retrieval strategies (Nusbaum et al., 2014), which can facilitate idea generation (Beatty & Silvia, 2012; Kenett et al., 2014), but may ultimately compromise the creativity of ideas (Gonthier & Besançon, 2024). Thus, comparing a creativity-focused instruction to a neutral instruction could help isolate whether the effect stems from promoting creativity specifically, rather than from differences in strategies introduced by focusing on either creativity or fluency.

Conclusion

Across two preregistered experiments, we demonstrated that activated creativity translates into creative confidence, especially among individuals who can accurately assess their own idea creativity. People who performed better upon the explicit “be creative” instruction perceived themselves as more creative than those completing the task less creatively in the “be fluent” condition. This mediation of idea creativity offers experimental support for the abilities-shape-confidence effect: individuals build creative self-perceptions based on their expressed creative abilities. However, accuracy further moderates this link—those with more accurate self-assessments showed stronger links between idea creativity and confidence. This effect may have further implications for educational and professional settings, where interventions aimed at enhancing creative performance, along with creative self-perception and metacognitive insight, could lead to changes in creative behavior.

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